

The effects of propagule pressure on the speed of invasion

Andriamihaja Ramanantoanina ^{a,b}

^aCenter for Invasion Biology, Department of Mathematical Sciences, University of Stellenbosch. ^bAfrican Institute for Mathematical Sciences. Contact: ar@aims.ac.za
Supervision team: Dr. Cang Hui and Dr. Aziz Ouhinou

Introduction

Although propagule pressure can evidently promote the success of establishment^[1], how it affects the speed of range expansion at the last stage of biological invasion has not been thoroughly explored. Classic spread models often assume that there is no variation in the dispersal ability of the initial propagules. This assumption has clearly over-simplified the reality as real propagules differ in their dispersal abilities^[2]. We here investigate how propagule composition (i.e. the number and variation of initial propagules in terms of their dispersal abilities) affects the speed of subsequent range expansion.

The model

We consider a population in which individuals have different level of dispersal ability. We assume that the dispersal ability is inheritable. The number of individuals with the level- i dispersal ability at time $t + 1$ and location x can be given as:

$$u_i(t + 1, x) = \int k_i(x - y)g_i(u_1, \dots, u_n)dy.$$

The population growth g_i follows the Ricker model

$$g_i(u_1, \dots, u_n) = u_i e^{r(1 - \sum_{j=1}^n u_j/K)}$$

and k_i can be either the Gaussian or Laplace dispersal kernel:

$$k_i^{\text{Gaussian}}(x - y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi d_i}} e^{-\frac{(x-y)^2}{4d_i}} \text{ and } k_i^{\text{Laplace}}(x - y) = \frac{1}{2d_i} e^{-\frac{|x-y|}{d_i}}.$$

The figures presented in the results section were obtained using Gaussian dispersal kernels. The results are qualitatively similar for the Laplace kernel.

Symbols description

Symbol	Description
U_0	Number of initial propagules introduced, assumed to be randomly drawn from a lognormal distribution $\log N(\mu, \sigma)$
σ	Variance of dispersal abilities across different levels
d_i	Dispersal ability of level i . For Gaussian dispersal kernel, d_i is the diffusion rate [km ² /yr] and for Laplace dispersal kernel d_i is dispersal distance [km/yr]
k_i	Dispersal kernel of individuals with the level- i dispersal ability
r	Intrinsic population growth rate
K	Carrying capacity
g_i	Population growth rate of individuals with the level- i dispersal ability
u_i	Number of individuals with the level- i dispersal ability
u	Combined population size
c	Asymptotic speed of range expansion

Results: Spatial sorting

The model leads to a spatial assortment of individuals with different dispersal abilities. Specifically, the population at the expanding range front comprises of individuals with strong dispersal abilities, whereas the population at the core comprises of individuals with weak dispersal abilities.

Results: Instantaneous speed

Numerical simulations show that the instantaneous speed of range expansion (dots) can be depicted by $2\sqrt{rd_{\text{front}}}$ (solid line) and $2(1 + \frac{r}{4})\sqrt{rd_{\text{front}}^2}$ for the Gaussian and Laplace kernels respectively, where d_{front} is the mean dispersal ability at the range front.

Results: Asymptotic speed

The asymptotic speed of range expansion is by

$$c = 2\sqrt{rD} \text{ and } c = 2\left(1 + \frac{r}{4}\right)\sqrt{rD^2}$$

respectively for the Gaussian and Laplace dispersal kernels with

$$D = e^\mu e^{\sqrt{2\sigma^2} \text{erf}^{-1}(2^{(1-1/U_0)} - 1)}$$

where erf^{-1} is the inverse of the error function.

The speed of range expansion increases with the initial propagule size (U_0) and the variation of dispersal abilities in the initial propagules (σ) (Left figure)

To test the performance of this formula, we ran 15 simulations for each pair of U_0 and σ . The asymptotic speed of range expansion predicted from the formula fits extremely well with the observation from the simulation (Right figure).

Discussion

This work highlights the importance of propagule size and composition to the speed of range expansion.

- The variation of dispersal ability in the initial propagules can lead to an assortment of individuals during range expansion, with strong dispersers concentrated at the range front;
- Both the instantaneous and asymptotic speed of range expansion are determined by the dispersal rate of the population at the range front. Therefore, predictions based on dispersal abilities obtained from the core population would be likely to underestimate the real speed of range expansion;
- The formula is proved to provide a reliable estimate of the speed of range expansion;
- Overall, increase of propagule variation (σ) can lead to an exponential increase of the asymptotic speed of range expansion.

References

- [1] Lockwood et al. TRENDS in Ecology and Evolution, Vol.20 (2005). [2] Korsu and Huusko. Aquatic invasions, Vol.4 (2009).